

DRIVING WORK AND LIFE ON PARALLEL LINES WHILE GROWING AS AN ENTREPRENEURS

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ABSTRACT

Work-Life Balance has recently taken the attention of both researchers and executives. This subject interests almost everyone with the professional career. For those who think that the main objective in life is to work, their career becomes the core of life. However, people have limited time and therefore have to perform many other activities other than their jobs. Intentionally people don't prefer imbalance between work and life. The difficulty which the most entrepreneurs are facing is that they just don't know how to make it happen for themselves.

In this study Work Life Balance is analyzed from the entrepreneur and employee context. The paper will help us to know the importance of Work-Life Balance with some insights and the measures to avoid unbalanced Work-Life situation for the success of ecommerce business.

Keywords: Work–life balance, working hours, Entrepreneurs

WORK LIFE BALANCE

Work-Life Balance is a significant issue of human resource management which is essential in promoting individual and organizational effectiveness. Work-life Balance is a wider concept which includes proper prioritizing between work and life on the other. Other terms that are used to refer to Work Life Balance include work-family Balance, work-family conflict and family friendly policies are other terms used in work-life balance concept. The issue has gained importance as there has been a substantial increase in work which is attributed to growing changes in information technology, by an intense, competitive work environment, extremely fast pace of change, constant deadlines and high targets.

In the phase of 1960's the issues related to working mothers and their struggle between work and children was considered as a work-life concern. After that in 1980's the policies and benefits for the women employee began to change which includes flexi time, employee assistant program (EAPs), home based work, maternity leave. In the duration of 1980's the male employees also raised the voice for the benefits, by the end the scope of work-life balance had been widened not only on women's but also on male employees, families and organizations. In 1990s it was become a vital issue to recognize the work-life balance for everyone –all employees, parents and non-parents, singles, and couples. The result of human resource was

unacceptable in the primary five years of twenty-first century due the reason of bad implementation The organizations were built the policies of work-life like health insurance, vacation, benefits, and EAP or education programs or flexible work policies but the policies were not implemented properly .It is important to reinforce what the organizations are offering with the proper execution.

In today's world the problem of unbalancing has seen universally, whether it is between the work and life or between principles and living or between men and women. Good balancing between work and life leads to high level of satisfaction which results better service. To find the priority between work and personal life is a huge challenge for every personal. Stress, unhappiness, health problems are the causes of poor balancing between work and life.

Work-Life Balance

As an equation: Mental resources + emotional resources + physical resources (including your time) = achieving your personal goals & fulfilling your responsibilities

Operational definitions

➤ **Work life balance**

Greenhaus, Collins and Shaw (2003) define work-life balance as the extent to which an Individual is equally engaged in – and equally satisfied with – his or her work role and family role. Thus, employees who experience high work-life balance are those who exhibit similar investment of time and commitment, to work and non-work domains.

➤ **Work personal life enhancement/ enrichment**

Work personal life enhancement or Work-family enrichment refers to “the extent to which experiences in one role improve the quality of life in the other role” (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). It has also been defined as “the extent to which participation at work (or home) is made easier by virtue of the experiences, skills, and opportunities gained or developed at home (or work)” (Frone, 2003).

➤ **Work/life conflict**

“A form of inter role conflict in which the role pressures from the work and family domains are mutually incompatible in some respect”, (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Conflict is a manifestation of stress due to competing role demands; conflict is considered a bi-directional construct, in that work can interfere with family (i.e., work-to-family conflict and family can interfere with work (i.e., family-to-work conflict (Frone, 2003).

Objectives:

- To evaluate the impact of pressure of work on personal goals.
- To identify the measures taken by entrepreneurs for balancing.
- Explain the benefits of work life balance.

- Recognize the signs of an unbalanced life.

RESERCH METHODOLOGY

Presently the data is collected from the secondary source that is from the reference books, journals, articles and websites. For further study the data will be collected from primary and secondary sources.

IMPORTANCE OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE

A healthy balance between work and home should be a priority for everyone. Implementing proper work-life balance offers many important benefits.

BENEFITS

- Benefits to company
 - Reduce absenteeism
 - Reduce staff turnover rates
 - Improved productivity
 - Enhanced organizational image
 - Employee loyalty
 - Retention of employee
- Benefits to employee
 - Increased job satisfaction
 - Better physical and mental health
 - A greater sense of job security
 - Reduce job stress levels
 - Control over work-life environment

There are, however, many hazards linked with an unbalanced work and home life.

- **Risks**
 - **Poor health:** Working long hours without taking time to relax will take its toll on health.
 - **Unresolved conflict:** A lack of balance can create conflicts at work and at home.
 - **Poor performance:** Taking on too much responsibility will lead to exhaustion and cause performance to suffer.
 - **Financial loss:** The impact on health and productivity takes a financial toll on both individual employees and organizations.

Signs of unbalancing

- **Health Risks**

Imbalance promotes poor health. Over time, this can lead to devastating, and possibly life changing consequences.

- **Absenteeism**

Poor health increases employee absenteeism and thus is a costly problem for entrepreneurs. There are hidden and direct costs that must be paid when an employee is absent from work.

- **Burnout**

Most people know that overworked employees eventually burnout. Burnout is the physical and psychological response to long-term stress.

- **Signs of Burnout:**

- **Loss of interest:** Burned-out employees cannot make themselves care about their work, which is the source of their stress.
- **Lack of emotion:** Emotional responses are abnormal when someone is burned-out.
- **Loss of motivation:** Former motivators no longer are effective.
- **Possible depression:** Burnout is closely linked to depression.

FROM THE ENTREPRENEUR'S SIDE

Entrepreneurs have the opportunity to improve work-life balance for their employees and increase productivity at the same time. Using the resources that entrepreneurs have at their disposal to change work conditions may seem counterproductive, but they are effective.

- **Offer More Employee Control**

Traditionally, entrepreneurs set all of the parameters concerning jobs. Keeping all of the control, however, augments stress on employees. Simply offering employees more control over their lives and establishing better work life balance will help alleviate this stress. Studies show that employee control actually increases loyalty and productivity. There are many ways to offer employees control, and we will go over some of them in detail in a later module.

Ways to control:

- Flex time
- Job sharing
- Telecommuting
- Job sharing

- **Ask Employees for Suggestions**

Employees have some of the best ideas on how to improve their jobs and the company as a whole. These ideas, however, are not always communicated. Many employees do not feel that people in management care and most managers do not have the time to sit down with each employee. The best way to hear about new, innovative ideas is to create an employee suggestion program.

- **Employee Assistance Program (EAP)**

Given the unavoidable stress of life, most people face times when they need assistance. EAPs provide employees access to counseling and other services. Without the aid of EAP counselors, the effects of stress can spiral out of control. Employee assistance programs give individuals the opportunity to seek help and learn the skills necessary to improve their work life balance.

➤ **Reward Your Staff**

This may seem basic, but rewarding your staff is an effective method for promoting work-life balance. Employees who feel appreciated are more confident, and rewards reinforce the behavior you want to see repeated. Rewards can also provide breaks that reduce stress. Rewards do not have to break the bank. There are simple ways to thank your employees for their service.

FROM THE EMPLOYEE'S SIDE

- Spend time with your family.
- Set working hours for yourself.
- Schedule time for your children so that you can attend a few special events.
- Video record the special events you'll have to miss, such as birthdays, League games, ballet recitals, etc. Watch them together.
- Proper communication with your partner, if you missed the calls arrange a time for you to call home.
- **Set up a separate phone line**
- Don't forget to take time throughout the day
- Don't be afraid to be flexible
- Work out at a gym.
- Attend workshops or hobby clubs that interest you; you'll have something in common with those you meet.
- Develop a circle of friends who understand your work schedule and are willing to be flexible in order to spend time with you.
- Bring up problems early and resolve them – before they threaten relationships.
- Get involved with activities - bowling, skiing and tennis.
- Make use of technology for conferencing like Skype.

CONCLUSION

Life without work is not possible. We spend most of our time at work, our position at work shows where we are heading and where we are now. Job is essential as it gives us a social status. It tells us where we live in this competitive world. But as work is important, Life & leisure is equally important. At the end of the day we work for the betterment of our life. Work-life balance is about creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will enable employees to have balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus strengthen employee loyalty and productivity.

In order to build and grow a successful business that allows you provide for yourself, your employees, and your family and keep your personal life, professional relationships, physical health, and mental sanity intact, need to have perfect equation of work and life.

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